

Occupational health aspects and regulations on airborne fibrous and non-fibrous dust

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SUMMARY: The particle deposition in the human respiratory tract is due to particle impaction, interception, sedimentation and diffusion. Many ultra fine dusts or fibres can produce free radicals in lung tissue. Free radicals are one of several important factors for the outcome of fibrosis and lung cancer. For this reason it is important to keep the dust exposure low if the health effect are unknown.

Only respirable fibres are known to be a potential health risk to the respiratory system during normal handling. No non-respirable fibre is known as carcinogenic in the respiratory tract. The European Commission has taken a new regulation for silicate fibres, refractory ceramic fibres have decided as possible carcinogenic. Other man made vitreous fibres is classified as possible carcinogenic or not depending on the fibre chemical content. WHO has evaluated the research of para-Aramide fibrils and find no evidence to classify these fibrils as possible carcinogenic.

KEYWORDS: fibre, fragments, size, health, dust, airborne, solubility, lung disease.

INTRODUCTION

All airborne contaminants that we are exposed to will to certain degree pass into the human body. The health effects of the contaminants depend on dose, physical and chemical properties. All contaminants have an effect in the human body. The health effects are mostly very low and we can ignore them. Some contaminants have higher effects on our health, which in some cases have lead to a decision to mark the chemical as dangerous. For the most chemicals this decision is not obvious. From a health point of view the ideal is to classify all unhealthy substances as dangerous. However in practise all unhealthy chemicals can not be forbidden. There are other factors than health involved in the judgement. Many chemicals are necessary in our community if we want our standard of living. The limit to classify a chemical as dangerous depends on many factors and there exist no exact limit.

Another problem is that there are no simple test methods with good accuracy to check health effects especially for particles and fibrous dust. This uncertainly to predict the effects of dust exposure leaves the floor open for surprises. An example, now there is safe evidence that silica except silicosis also produces cancer [1]. Now is silica classified as a carcinogenic substance. This lead to the uncertain situation that occupational health hazard of fibrous dust is controversial. Recent regulation for vitreous mineral fibres has emphasised this. Among the important physical and chemical factors for the health risk assessment of airborne dust, fibres

and fragments are particle size, shape, surface chemistry, solubility, toxicity and mechanical properties. In this paper we will only discuss the health effects from particles and fibres that not have a rapid acute toxicity (poisonous) or reactivity (etching).

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Particle and fibre size

For occupational disease related to the particles and dust chemistry is only one important factor. Also the physical factors are important, in this case the aerodynamic properties, particle size, shape and density. The particle deposition in the human respiratory tract is due to particle impaction, interception, sedimentation and diffusion. Only fine particles may reach the alveolar region of the lungs, i.e. the region of the active gas exchange. The aerodynamic particle size corresponding to 50% penetration (of total airborne dust) through the larynx is approx. 10 micrometer and the size corresponding to 50% penetration down to the gas-exchange region (alveolar region) of the lung is approx. 4 micrometer.

Some types of hardwood dust are known to be toxic and to cause cancer in the nose region, poly-aromatic hydrocarbons cause cancer in the thoracic region and quartz causes silicosis in the gas exchange region. Particle size related TLV-values are used for work place health risk assessments such as inhalable dust (total dust) for all particle sizes and respirable dust for particles <5 micron. There is also a thoracic standard for particles <10 micron. Outdoor there is a standard close to thoracic named PM₁₀ (10 micron cut off) and a standard for fine dust PM_{2.5} (2.5 micron cut off).

In occupational health studies a fibre is defined as a particle with an aspect ratio (length/width) >3:1. The deposition in the human airways mainly depends on the fibre diameter. Fibres of diameters <3 micron are regarded as respirable. Fibres splintered in fragments with a length/width ratio <3:1 are regarded as non fibrous dust. Today the fibre diameter is estimated from microscopy. Work is going on to alter the standard from the geometrically estimated fibre diameter to an aerodynamically estimated fibre diameter.

No non-respirable fibres are known to be a potential health risk to the respiratory system during normal handling. The European Commission has classified man made vitreous fibres as non-carcinogenic if the diameter is >6 micron [2]. Respirable thin long fibres are more dangerous than respirable short thick fibres. Later research has shown that fibre length of approximately 20 micron can be more danger [3] than shorter and longer fibres. Earlier the opinion was that longer fibres were more dangerous than shorter without any limitation in length.

Fragments of most types of continuous fibres used in composites are not respirable. However, thinner fibres are in many respects very attractive and give increased specific surface and usually better mechanical performance due to statistical effects and decreased internal stress build-up due to bending. Fibres of diameter below 3 micron can form respirable fibrous dust, but splitting or release of dust formed during manufacturing or handling can also give respirable dust.

A problem is that the low bending stiffness of thin respirable fibres makes the fibres more attractive for the workers in the handling processes due to a soft feeling instead of the stickiness of the thicker fibres. Fibres with high bending stiffness can however penetrate skin and

cause irritation and dermatology problems and also less handling sensitivity, especially in the fingertips. There is of course other dermatology health effects from non-respirable fibres as allergy from epoxy and skin cancer from carbon fibre produced from tar pitch [4].

Other physical and chemical factors

The time from exposure until the disease is recognised is long for many dusts and fibres, in many cases over 30 year. Earlier this made it difficult to understand the connection between exposure and disease. The lifetime of a particle in the respiratory system is significant for the risk of lung diseases. Therefore, particle solubility in lung tissue is a very important factor. Asbestos and silica are chemically extremely stable. Respirable wollastonite and some glass fibres are examples on material that have a short lifetime in lung tissue. If the dust or fibres are the same or more soluble the expected health effect are low. The European Commission has classified some fibrous material as non-cancerogenic if biological durability after inhalation is less than 10 days [2].

The ability of the lung clearance system to protect the lung and transport the dust is of course important. Smoking and high exposures to air pollutants reduce the effectiveness of the lung clearance system.

Another important factor for cancer is that almost all ultra fine dusts or fibres can produce free radicals in lung tissue. The experience from several tests are that almost every tested dust can cause free radicals [5] in lung tissue, so most dust are potential carcinogenic or potential to cause fibrosis until the opposite has been shown. In the evaluation of the cancer risk of the fibres other chemical influences are also discussed, especially the iron content of the fibre.

It is also important not to forget the surface chemicals that fibres usually are manipulated by for example the use of spin finishes and sizings in order to improve handling and performance. Today epoxy allergy from prepreg is a common problem. During handling of epoxy sized continuous carbon fibres [6] or glass fibres [7] were emitted fibre-shaped epoxy particles. At present, there is no literature about these epoxy fibres.

DUST AND FIBRE EXPOSURES

Very low concentrations of dust far below normal TLV-values can influence in our health. Experience from outdoors is PM_{2.5}-dust concentrations in order of 0.01 mg/m³ have small but detectable health effect on human. In work places maximal exposure for inhalable dust without any expected negative health influence is 10 -15 mg/m³. For respirable dust the limit normally is 5 mg/m³. From known health effects and hygienic considerations an acceptable exposure is expected to be within dust concentration range of 0.001 - 10 mg/m³. The concentration 0.01 mg/m³ is a very low concentration. In most industrial productions it is not economically realistic to reach such low concentrations. Before introducing new materials more specific risk assessment are necessary. A problem is that animal exposure experiments give a very poor information of acceptable dose for human. To make a decision on maximal acceptable exposure level we must combine the experience from animal exposure with known health effects on humans from materials with similar physics and chemistry.

To give a picture of exposures in different environments we will give some examples of inhalable dust levels. Normal values indoor in non-smoking area and outdoor air are <0.1 mg/m³. Normal background concentrations in workshops are 0.1 - 1 mg/m³. Dusty operations

as grinding, welding with poor process ventilation and foundries, steel plant can often emit higher values.

The health effects of different occupational respirable fibre exposure have resulted in three regulated levels, 0 f/ml for the most dangerous substances, 0.1 - 0.5 f/ml if the fibres cause cancer or fibrosis and 1-10 f/ml if the risk for lung diseases are low or negative. If a dusty fibrous material is handled carefully the respirable fibre concentration can be kept below 1 f/ml. To keep a dusty fibre material with high content of respirable fibres below 0.1 f/ml there is a need for heavy dust reducing equipment.

If there is no or poor knowledge of a material's health effects, we recommend the use of other alternatives with better documentation. If there are no alternative our recommendation is to reduce the dust or fibre concentration to a safe level below 0.1 f/ml.

HEALTH EFFECTS AND REGULATIONS OF SOME FIBROUS MATERIALS

During handling the non-respirable continuous aramid-fibres can be split into respirable fibrils. Only few fibres split during normal handling. OSHA has reported concentrations around 0.2 f/ml [4]. Our own experience is that there are works that give higher concentrations, for example cutting by water jet produced air concentrations over 1 f/ml. These thin para-aramid fibrils have shown a low pulmonary fibrosis in rats. Some cytotoxic activity to cells has been observed, but the evaluation today is that there is no safe evidence to classify para-aramid as carcinogenic [1]. The dust from continuously aramide fibres are like many other fibres used in advanced composite more or less skin irritating [8].

Non-respirable carbon fibres are known to not produce fibrosis and lung cancer. Also if the fibres are produced from coal tar pitch [4]. A test with thinner carbon fibres is reported. The carbon fibres were made from polyacrylonitrile fibres. They were 3.5 micron in diameter and 72% were 10-60 µm long. No effects due to the exposure were seen [9]. The research of coal dust has not shown adequate evidence for carcinogenic effects in human's [1].

The fibrosis and carcinogenic effect to many silicate fibres has been investigated during several years. The European Commission has decided that man made vitreous (silicate) fibres with random orientation with alkaline oxide or earth oxide ($N_2O + K_2O + CaO + MgO + BaO$) greater than 18% by weight should not be classified as carcinogenic. If the concentration of these alkali or earth oxide content is equal or <18 % the material is classified as carcinogenic [2]. Refractory Ceramic Fibres is one example of the last group.

Saffil fibres (aluminium oxide) are respirable. As for para-aramid fibrils the reported health effects from animal tests show a very low reaction to Saffil fibres [10-12].

We have not found any publication on the health effects of non-respirable continuous silicon carbide fibres. For the shorter and respirable silicon carbide whiskers there are results indicating both fibrosis and lung cancer [13-17].

Wollastonite, both as synthetic and natural fibres, is not classified, as a carcinogenic to human's [1]. Wollastonite fibres are for instance used in ceramic composites.

In the futures one can expect that new non-respirable and respirable fibres will be introduced in advanced composites. The toxicology knowledge is often limited for new materials and our recommendation is to be careful during handling and machining of any new fibres.

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